

RESPONSE OF COMPOSITE PANELS SUBJECTED TO NEAR-FIELD BLAST LOADING

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Abstract

Experimental studies were performed to understand the near-field blast response of composite panels when exposed to near-field explosive loading in different environments. The panel construction under consideration was an e-glass fiber-reinforced composite laminate infused with Derakane 8084 vinyl ester resin. The panel was layered bi-axially with woven fiber orientations of 0° and 90°. Panel dimensions were approximately 203 mm x 203 mm x 1 mm (8 in x 8 in x 0.04 in). Experiments were carried out with the panel fully clamped in a holding fixture, which was in turn fastened inside a water tank. The fixture was fastened in such a way as to allow for explosive loading experiments in the following environments: submerged with water backing, submerged with air backing, and air immersion with air backing. A stereo Digital Image Correlation [DIC] system was employed to capture the full-field dynamic behavior of the panel during the explosive event. Since light travels through water before entering the cameras, it distorts the coordinates of the speckle pattern on the specimen. In order to overcome this problem, calibration experiments were first performed to develop an algorithm to account for the refractive index difference between water and air. Results indicated that the immersion environment contributes significantly to the blast response of the material and to the specimens' appreciable damage characteristics.

2 Digital Image Correlation

Digital Image Correlation [DIC] is a powerful optical tool in experimental mechanics that seeks to non-intrusively ascertain full-field displacement,

strain, and velocity fields associated with a deforming body. The method is accomplished via use of high speed digital cameras and specialized analytical software [1]. To record the deformation in real time, two high speed digital cameras are employed in a synchronized stereo arrangement. Calibration of the cameras is achieved via use of an image calibration grid, consisting of a white field and a distinct pattern of evenly-spaced points. The grid is rotated and translated in- and out-of-plane, as a series of individual photographs are taken by the stereo camera system. The predetermination of the calibration points' spacing allows the analytical software to track the points' center point displacement in a coordinate plane unique to both cameras. The software then correlates the images in these planes to establish a real-world coordinate system from which full-field, three-dimensional deformation measurements are made [2]. Before experiments, the observation side of the deforming body is painted with a random black-and-white speckle pattern. This random pattern creates a diverse field of unique pixel intensity subsets whose displacements, during specimen deformation, are photographically captured by the high speed cameras. The analytical software tracks and interprets these displacements, which allows consequently for the three-dimensional assessment of strain, velocity, and other applicable parameters [3]. Two Photron Fastcam SA1.1 cameras were employed in this study, in conjunction with Vic-3D analysis software, produced by Correlated Solutions.

2.1 MATLAB Transformation Code

Several experiments were undertaken completely in water. During these, the images captured of the panel specimen passed through water before

interfacing with the DIC cameras' Charge Coupled Device [CCD]. The refractive index of water thereby distorted the specimens' DIC speckle patterns, and imposed the need for an image transformation algorithm so as to observe accurate deformations. Such a method was proposed by Haile using the engineering software, MATLAB [4]. Gracia produced a modified version and validated it experimentally [5]. The employed algorithm compliments an aspect of the experimental process whereby a set of images is taken of a fastened DIC calibration grid in water and then, without moving the grid, a corresponding set is taken of the grid in air. These image sets are imported to the MATLAB algorithm, wherein a representative image pair, consisting of a distorted underwater image and its corresponding undistorted "dry" image, is loaded into a MATLAB-based image editor. The nonlinear special distortion between the submerged image and the dry image is ascertained by selecting at least 12 corresponding points on the calibration grid images. Applying these selected points to identical locations on each of the remaining image pairs, the algorithm then develops a unique image transformation matrix that maps the distorted coordinates of the submerged images to the undistorted coordinates of the dry images. The matrix thus developed is then applied to each DIC photograph taken during the UNDEX event so as to make similar corrections. This image correction method was demonstrated to produce strain values with 5%-10% better correlation to theory than uncorrected images [5].

3 Material/Specimen

The material considered in this analysis was an e-glass/vinyl ester resin [EVE laminate, manufactured at TPI Composites in Warren, R.I. The laminate was layered biaxially using two layers of woven fiber sheets. The individual sheets were woven with combined fiber orientations of 0° and 90°, and possessed an aerial density of 0.61 kg/m² (18 oz/yd²). A vacuum assisted resin transfer was employed to saturate the layered sheets with Derakane 8084 vinyl ester resin. The resulting laminate was divided into 203 mm x 203 mm x 1 mm (8 in x 8 in x 0.04 in) panel specimens. After cutting, these panels were subsequently post cured sequentially at 70° C for 2 hours and 60 °C for 10

hours. The panel surface area designed to be subjected to the explosive wave front was 152 mm x 152 mm (6 in x 6 in), allowing for a 25.4 mm (1 in) clamping edge. 15 screw holes, of 7.94 mm diameter (0.3125 in.), were spaced at intervals around the periphery to fit over ¼-20 mounting screws protruding from the holding fixture. The specimen geometry is shown in Fig. 1. The experimental area of interest on each specimen was painted white, upon which coat a black dot matrix was spray painted using a perforated metal mesh. A random black speckle pattern was subsequently hand-painted over these coats, for recognition by the DIC data acquisition technique.

4 Experimental Method

A schematic of the experimental setup is depicted in Fig. 2. A raised steel box comprised the holding fixture into which the specimen was fully clamped, exposing a total specimen area of 152 mm x 152 mm (6 in x 6 in) to the UNDEX event. The box was positioned in the experimental water tank close to the transparent Lexan observation window to enable proper airtight sealing for air backed experiments in a water environment. The box was also capable of being secured farther away from the observation window for experiments that did not require an airtight seal. The pressure sensors employed in the underwater experiments were two series W138A05 integrated circuit piezoelectric [ICP] tourmaline underwater blast probes produced by PCB Piezotronics, Inc. The tourmaline sensing element was suspended in a silicone oil-filled flexible transparent tube of diameter 9.4 mm (0.37 in.), and the overall probe length was 193 mm (7.6 in.). The probes were mounted vertically. The pressure sensors employed in air experiments were two series 137A21 integrated circuit piezoelectric (ICP) free field blast probes produced by PCB Piezotronics, Inc. The distance from the conical probe tip to the quartz sensing element was 157 mm (6.2 in), and the overall probe length was 406 mm (16 in). The sensors were mounted horizontally with the sensing diaphragm oriented sideways. The DIC and side view cameras were oriented as seen in Fig. 2.

4.1 Water Submersion, Air Backing

Experiments were performed to investigate the response of the EVE composite specimen to a near-field blast event in an experimental environment characterized by water submersion and air backing—an environment referred to hereafter as “water/air”. For each experiment conducted thus, silicone caulk was used to fill the 3.18 mm (0.125 in) clearance between the experimental holding box to the transparent Lexan viewing window, thereby sealing the edges. A thin bead of silicone caulk was likewise applied around the edges of the EVE composite specimen, in an appropriate area as to seal the holding box’s interior air environment from the exterior water environment. A specimen mounting bracket was bolted over the EVE panel to establish a fully-clamped boundary condition. The RP-503 detonator was suspended on the water side of the composite panel by fishing line at a distance of 76.2 mm (3 in.) from the center of the specimen. Two tourmaline underwater blast probes were positioned vertically with their sensing elements at radial distances of 160 mm (6.3 in.) and 226 mm (8.9 in.) from the detonator; these sensors were designated ‘sensor 1’ and ‘sensor 2,’ respectively. 100 mm DIC camera lenses were employed, and the camera frame rate was set to 20,000 frames per second (FPS), rendering a DIC image resolution of 512 x 512, and an inter-frame time of 50 μ sec. The RP-503 charge was detonated by an independent firing box, which was wired to an isolated electrical circuit to minimize the risk of power surges influencing the recording oscilloscope. The deflections of the speckle patterns on each specimen were observed by the DIC cameras and processed by the DIC software. Out-of-plane deflections were measured from the plane of the un-deformed specimen. The pressure waves induced by the RP-503 explosion were detected by the tourmaline blast probes. These millivolt signals were amplified to ± 10 VDC signals by an in-line conditioner and relayed to a recording oscilloscope. The oscilloscope was commanded to trigger from a rising voltage of 400 mV from sensor 1.

The first experiment of this set yielded results that were repeatable and consistent with the ensuing experiments, as seen in Fig. 3 (discussed in section 5). The composite specimen’s center point deflected sharply outward to a global positive maximum of 27.44 mm (1.08 in.) after a total elapsed time of 1.3

msec, before beginning to rebound inward. An X-shaped plateau that occurred across the panel’s center during the rebound forced the center point outward briefly, observable at approximately 3 msec. This brief center point response was followed by a rapid center point collapse to an intermediate negative deflection of approximately -14 mm (-0.55 in.) at approximately 7 msec elapsed time. Following a dwell of approximately 2.2 msec at -14 mm, the panel center point collapsed further to a global maximum negative deflection of -23.9 mm (-0.94 in.) at 15.3 msec total elapsed time. The center point deflection tended modestly and nominally outward for an additional 6 msec, before expanding rapidly outward to a local positive maximum of 17.43 mm (0.69 in.) at 27.15 msec total elapsed time. The apparent structural response of the plate caused minor oscillatory center point motion, before settling to a final recorded deflection of 15.64 mm (0.62 in.) at 32.05 msec. This behavior is represented in Fig. 4. *Post mortem* damage was observed to include panel delamination and fiber tearing around the boundary. Such tearing was observed in later experiments to have propagated through the specimen. A *post mortem* image of the specimen may be observed in Fig. 5. A typical pressure pulse is represented in Fig. 6.

Maximum positive deflections for water/air experiments 2 through 4 were recorded to be 29.61 mm (1.17 in.), 26.02 mm (1.02 in.), and 27.83 mm (1.1 in.), respectively; corresponding maximum negative deflections were -27.25 mm (-1.07 in.), -25.45 mm (-1.00 in.), and -28.99 mm (-1.14 in.). Experiments 3 and 4 employed a side view camera with a 28 mm lens to observe the development and dissipation of the gas bubble produced as a result of the detonation. The bubble in experiment 3 was observed to expand in radius until an elapsed event time between 11.10 – 14.05 msec, before it reversed direction and achieved full collapse at approximately 22.15 msec. The bubble in experiment 4 expanded until a time between 10.25 – 13.30 msec, and achieved full collapse by approximately 22.60 msec.

4.2 Water Submersion, Water Backing

Experiments were performed to investigate the response of the EVE composite specimen to a near-field blast event in an experimental environment

characterized by water submersion and water backing—an environment referred to hereafter as “water/water”. Because water was recognized to be incompressible, it was feared that, with a clearance of just 3.16 mm (0.125 in) between the box edge and the transparent Lexan viewing window, the water within the holding box of the experimental fixture would significantly dampen the panel specimen’s deflection during the UNDEX event. The holding box was subsequently moved backwards on the mounting stand and re-bolted, so as to provide sufficient clearance to allow proper water circulation while the panel flexed. The mounting/boundary conditions, the detonator/blast probes and their positioning, the camera lenses, settings, and software, and the supporting data acquisition devices employed in the water/water experiment set remained identical to those employed in the water/air set. The specialized MATLAB program described in section 2.1 was utilized in each experiment to develop appropriate image transformation matrices. A side view camera with a 28 mm lens was again employed to observe the development and dissipation of the gas bubble produced as a result of the detonation—though, due to the effects of cavitation in front of the specimen, the side view images were rendered irrelevant, as shall be discussed later.

The first water/water experiment yielded repeatable results that remained consistent with those that followed. After the initiation of the explosion, the rapid flexing of the panel caused dense cavitation to develop in front of the specimen’s speckle pattern. The impenetrability of the cavitation field varied in intensity as the UNDEX event progressed, but the panel center point remained at all times beneath considerable shielding. Because of this, DIC information could only be confidently analyzed up to 200 μ sec after the onset of panel deflection, a maximum positive value of which was recorded as 2.31 mm (0.09 in.). The center point deflection plot from water/water experiment 1, typical of the water/water experiment set, is given in Fig. 7. *Post mortem* damage was observed to include mild delamination around the boundaries and the panel center. This damage is depicted in Fig. 8. Maximum 200 μ sec positive deflections for water/water experiments 2 and 3 were recorded to be 1.53 mm (0.09 in.) and 1.73 mm (0.06 in.), respectively.

4.3 Air Immersion, Air Backing

Experiments were performed to investigate the response of the EVE composite specimen to a near-field blast event in an experimental environment characterized by air immersion and air backing—an environment referred to hereafter as “air/air”. The tourmaline blast sensors were retired during the air/air experiments and replaced by air blast pencil probes. These sensors were mounted horizontally with the sensing element oriented sideways. The size of these instruments imposed different standoff distance requirements than those in the water/air and water/water experiment sets. The sensor tips were positioned at a minimum of 3 in. from the explosive, to avoid the creation of moments of force against the sensor bodies. With the tips of sensors 1 and 2 standing off at 76.3 mm (3 in.) and 152.4 mm (6 in.) (respectively) from the explosive, the 157.5 mm (6.2 in.) distance from the probe diaphragms to the tips imposed actual sensing element standoff distances of 233.7 mm (9.2 in.) and 309.9 mm (12.2 in.), respectively. In addition, due to incidental damage to the transparent Lexan viewing window, the window had to be removed from the tank. To protect the DIC lenses, special filter mounts were obtained for affixing to the lenses. Thin plates of Lexan were inserted into the filter mounts, which, owing to compatibility restrictions, could only be attached to 60 mm lenses.

The first air/air experiment, as with the water/air and water/water experiments, yielded repeatable data that remained consistent through the experiment set. The panel center point deflected to a positive maximum of 6.92 mm (0.27 in.) after an elapsed time of 0.4 msec. The ensuing center point deflection followed a pattern of successive outward and inward oscillations, first reaching its maximum negative of -9.51 mm (-0.37 in.) at an elapsed time of 1.05 msec, followed by several additional local positive and negative maxima. By approximately 7 msec, after 2 additional peaks beyond the first, the oscillatory motion deviated from its apparent vibrational response, lapsing instead into a square wave pattern characterized by prolonged ascents (~7 msec – ~12 msec) and ebbs (~15 msec – ~25.95 msec). This behavior, characteristic of the air/air series, is illustrated in Fig. 9. *Post mortem* damage

included light delamination and resin singeing around the boundary, and a prominent lacerated cleft that passed horizontally through the panel center. This cleft propagated through the panel's thickness, severing fibers on both sides. On the explosive side of the panel, the cleft appeared as a demarcation line between a dense lower field of delamination/impact damage pockmarks and isolated resin singeing, and a sparse upper field of delamination/impact damage pockmarks. This damage is depicted in Fig. 10. The incident pressure wave in air was registered in experiments 3 and 4, a representative plot of which is depicted in Fig. 11. The positive and negative pressure phases characteristic of an air blast are clearly visible [6, 7].

5 Discussion

Based on DIC data and/or *post mortem* specimen damage, it is apparent that the dissimilar media characterized by the water/air environment produced more drastic panel deformation than that experienced in the fully-immersed water environment. It is believed that this phenomenon was induced by the acoustic impedance differential encountered by the shock wave as it interfaced with, and passed through, the panel specimen. The acoustic impedance mismatch thus initiated a more intense reflected wave front, which interacted more violently with the panel in the moments following the UNDEX event, causing greater deflection, delamination, and through-thickness tearing around the panel boundary. Panels subjected to the air/air experimental environment experienced far less applied impulse than either of the water environments (Fig. 6, 11), as a result of the more rapid pressure decay in air. This provides additional context for the observed air/air behavior, in that the air/air maximum deflections, intermediate between the water/air and water/water deflections, were still achieved in spite of the applied shock load being significantly less.

Comparative analysis between the water/air and air/air full-event displacement behavior qualitatively suggests that fluid-structure interaction is quite different between the experimental environments, and that this difference is related to the mode forms of vibration witnessed during these events. In the first place, the center point deflections manifested

themselves with vastly different profiles. The water/air deflections followed a pattern indicative of severely damped vibration, with heavy dependence on the progress of the gas bubble. In water/air experiment 3, the maximum expansion of the bubble between approximately 11.10 and 14.05 msec coincided with the initiation of the panel's final inward flex to its global negative maximum (Fig. 12); the center point's steep outward rebound at ~23 msec initiated at approximately the same time as the bubble's final collapse at ~22.15 msec. Similar dependence was observed in water/air experiment 4. The air/air series, however, not subject to the cyclic expansion and contraction of bubble pulses, generated a displacement pattern indicative of natural frequency oscillation, followed by square wave ascents and ebbs. Even still, the air/air series displayed possible correlative behavior between the transition to square wave oscillations and the final combustion and dissipation of the explosion's gasses, evidenced by the side view images collected during air/air experiment 5.

In the second place, the full-field deflection profiles indicate different structural responses to the explosive load and fluid interaction. The water/air series center point deflection, after achievement of maximum positive displacement ~1 msec, displayed curious behavior during its inward flex when it briefly expanded outwards again in a miniature 'hump.' Upon examination of the full-field displacement contour plots (Fig. 3), it was seen that this intriguing occurrence was due to the panel's inward flex being ultimately dominated by symmetric movement around the boundary, driving the panel material towards the center and forcing the center point outward, abruptly and briefly reversing the center point's inward motion. The air/air full-field displacement contour plots (Fig. 13), up to an elapsed time shortly after 5 msec, indicate the presence of asymmetric mode forms that permitted center point to vibrate with, at best, modest stability through periods of distinct, sometimes near-constant frequency. This suggests vast differences in the fluid structure interaction associated with the two environments.

DIC results from the water/water series offer insight to a more-limited extent than do the results from the other two. The onset of cavitation, possibly due to flexing of the water tank's transparent Lexan

viewing window, compromised any DIC results after 200 μ sec, leaving only a very narrow window of time in which to interpret the data. However, it can still be reasonably deduced that the water/water series oscillation amplitudes were the least of the three experiment sets. Fig. 14 depicts an overlay of each series' average deflections over the first 200 μ sec of the UNDEX event. It is apparent that the water/water displacement was anemic by comparison, and when considered with the very mild *post mortem* specimen damage it could be reasonably concluded that the maximum panel deflections fell shorter than those of the water/air and air/air series.

6 Conclusions

This study examined the influence that certain operating environments have on the deflection and appreciable damage characteristics of fully-clamped composite panels when subjected to near-field explosive loadings. It was concluded that the mixed media environment of water submersion and air backing encouraged the greatest panel center point deflection and the most structurally-debilitating *post mortem* damage. Fluid structure interactions were recognized as contributing factors to the vibration mode forms exhibited in the transient center point and full-field deflection profiles, and panel deflection behavior was correlated with the expansion/contraction of the explosive gas bubble and the dissipation of gasses for the water/air and air/air series, respectively.

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Figure 1: The composite panel specimen, units in millimeters

Figure 4: Outward center point deflection typical of the water/air series

Figure 2: Schematic of the experimental setup

Figure 5: Post mortem damage typical of the water/air series

Figure 3: Progression of the X plateau mode form, characteristic of the water/air series

Figure 6: Peak overpressure and decay profile, registered at 160 mm (6.3 in.), typical of the decay in water

Figure 7: Outward center point deflection typical of the water/water series

Figure 8: Post mortem damage of water/water specimen 1, showing light delamination around the boundary (left) and center (right)

Figure 9: Outward center point deflection typical of the air/air series

Figure 10: Post mortem panel damage on the explosive side (top) and observation side (bottom)

Figure 11: Peak overpressure and decay profile, registered at 233.7 mm (9.2 in.), typical of the decay in air

Figure 12: Center point displacement of water/air experiment 3

Figure 13: Mode form observed during air/air experiment 5

Figure 14: Overlaid average displacement profiles for the first 200 μsec